

Supplementary material for manuscript Schaft and Brosig: "CSR in der deutschen Landwirtschaft" (CSR in German Agriculture)

Estimation results compiled in Table 2 of the manuscript (Stata log file)

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++  Z U S A M M E N H Ä N G E   m i t I N D E X: V_qrt  ++
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FAKTOR: Erbringen landw Betriebe zusätzliche Leistungen? (Bd2_Meinung)

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+-----+
| Key                                     |
+-----+
| frequency                               |
| expected frequency                       |
+-----+
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V_qrt-Vielfaltskl asse [P25, P75]	Erbringen landw Betriebe zusätzliche Leistungen?			Total
	2 stenz	3 stez	4 stvz	
unteres Quantil	3	6	43	52
	1.5	5.0	45.4	52.0
mittlere Quantile	3	11	89	103
	3.0	10.0	90.0	103.0
oberes Quantil	0	3	48	51
	1.5	5.0	44.6	51.0
Total	6	20	180	206
	6.0	20.0	180.0	206.0

Pearson chi2(4) = 4.3976 Pr = 0.355

margins Bd2_Meinung nach anova V_qrt Bd2_Meinung if Bd2_Meinung !=0

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 206

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

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|          |          Delta-method
|          |      Margin   Std. Err.    t    P>|t|    [95% Conf. Interval]
-----+-----
Bd2_Meinung |
  2 stenz |    36.23602   6.248091    5.80  0.000    23.91654    48.5555
  3 stez  |    47.9795   3.42222    14.02  0.000    41.23184    54.72715
  4 stvz  |    50.6511   1.14074    44.40  0.000    48.40188    52.90032
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```

Variables that uniquely identify margins: Bd2_Meinung
margins Bd2_Meinung, pwcompare nach anova V_qrt Bd2_Meinung

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 206

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

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|          |      Number of
|          |      Comparisons
-----+-----
Bd2_Meinung |              3
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|          |          Delta-method   Bonferroni   Bonferroni
|          |      Contrast   Std. Err.    t    P>|t|    [95% Conf. Interval]
-----+-----
Bd2_Meinung |
3 stez vs 2 stenz |    11.74347   7.12392    1.65  0.302    -5.453546    28.94049
4 stvz vs 2 stenz |    14.41508   6.351372    2.27  0.073     -.917022    29.74718
4 stvz vs 3 stez  |     2.671608   3.607337    0.74  1.000    -6.036441    11.37966
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Variables that uniquely identify margins: _pw

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
(file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_Bd2_Meinung.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

FAKTOR: Hauptausrichtung (Un05)

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-----+-----
| Key |
|-----|
|     |
| frequency |
| expected frequency |
|-----|
+-----+

```

Hauptausrichtung	V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]			Total
	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
-9 Nichtbeantwortet	0 0.3	0 0.5	1 0.2	1 1.0
1 Ackerbau	20 18.9	37 37.5	18 18.6	75 75.0
2 Futterbau	7 7.6	15 15.0	8 7.4	30 30.0
3 Veredelung	15 9.8	19 19.5	5 9.7	39 39.0
4 Gartenbau	0 0.3	0 0.5	1 0.2	1 1.0
5 Dauerkulturen	1 2.0	6 4.0	1 2.0	8 8.0
6 Pflanzenbau-Verbund	0 0.5	1 1.0	1 0.5	2 2.0
7 Viehhaltung-Verbund	1 2.3	7 4.5	1 2.2	9 9.0
8 Pflanzenbau-Viehhal	7 8.8	15 17.5	13 8.7	35 35.0
9 Sonstiges	1 1.5	3 3.0	2 1.5	6 6.0
Total	52 52.0	103 103.0	51 51.0	206 206.0

Pearson chi2(18) = 20.2649 Pr = 0.318

margins Un05 nach anova V_qrt Un05 if Un05 !=0
(1 observation deleted)

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 196

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

Un05	Delta-method				
	Margin	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]

1 Ackerbau	48.80686	1.744171	27.98	0.000	45.36644	52.24729
2 Futterbau	49.36442	2.757776	17.90	0.000	43.92463	54.80422
3 Veredelung	45.05381	2.41873	18.63	0.000	40.2828	49.82482
5 Dauerkulturen	52.39765	5.340411	9.81	0.000	41.86354	62.93176
7 Viehhaltung-Verbund	49.21847	5.034987	9.78	0.000	39.28682	59.15013
8 Pflanzenbau-Viehhaltung	55.28612	2.553205	21.65	0.000	50.24985	60.32239

Variables that uniquely identify margins: Un05
 margins Un05, pwcompare nach anova V_qrt Un05 if Un05 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 196

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Number of
	Comparisons
Un05	15

	Contrast	Delta-method Std. Err.	Bonferroni t	Bonferroni P> t	Bonferroni [95% Conf. Interval]	
Un05						
2 Futterbau vs 1 Ackerbau	.5575604	3.263045	0.17	1.000	-9.14273	10.25785
3 Veredelung vs 1 Ackerbau	-3.753053	2.98201	-1.26	1.000	-12.61789	5.111785
5 Dauerkulturen vs 1 Ackerbau	3.590789	5.618017	0.64	1.000	-13.1103	20.29188
7 Viehhaltung-Verbund vs 1 Ackerbau	.4116107	5.32853	0.08	1.000	-15.4289	16.25212
8 Pflanzenbau-Viehhaltung vs 1 Ackerbau	6.479255	3.092084	2.10	0.562	-2.712809	15.67132
3 Veredelung vs 2 Futterbau	-4.310614	3.668185	-1.18	1.000	-15.21529	6.594067
5 Dauerkulturen vs 2 Futterbau	3.033229	6.010434	0.50	1.000	-14.83442	20.90088
7 Viehhaltung-Verbund vs 2 Futterbau	-.1459497	5.740769	-0.03	1.000	-17.21195	16.92005
8 Pflanzenbau-Viehhaltung vs 2 Futterbau	5.921694	3.758216	1.58	1.000	-5.250626	17.09401
5 Dauerkulturen vs 3 Veredelung	7.343843	5.862614	1.25	1.000	-10.08438	24.77206
7 Viehhaltung-Verbund vs 3 Veredelung	4.164664	5.585817	0.75	1.000	-12.4407	20.77003
8 Pflanzenbau-Viehhaltung vs 3 Veredelung	10.23231	3.516974	2.91	0.061	-.2228569	20.68747
7 Viehhaltung-Verbund vs 5 Dauerkulturen	-3.179179	7.339692	-0.43	1.000	-24.99842	18.64006
8 Pflanzenbau-Viehhaltung vs 5 Dauerkulturen	2.888465	5.919361	0.49	1.000	-14.70845	20.48538
8 Pflanzenbau-Viehhaltung vs 7 Viehhaltung-Verbund	6.067644	5.645348	1.07	1.000	-10.71469	22.84998

Variables that uniquely identify margins: _pw

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
 (file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_Un05.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

FAKTOR: LF <=50, >50 (LFK12)

LF <=50, >50	V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]			Total
	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
1 <=50	19	33	6	58
2 >50	32	68	42	142
Total	51	101	48	200

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+-----+
| Key       |
+-----+
| frequency |
| expected frequency |
+-----+

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LF <=50, >50	V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]			Total
	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
1 <=50	19 14.8	33 29.3	6 13.9	58 58.0
2 >50	32 36.2	68 71.7	42 34.1	142 142.0
Total	51 51.0	101 101.0	48 48.0	200 200.0

Pearson chi2(2) = 8.6965 Pr = 0.013

Number of obs = 200 R-squared = 0.0374
 Root MSE = 15.0366 Adj R-squared = 0.0325

Source	Partial SS	df	MS	F	Prob>F
Model	1738.3081	1	1738.3081	7.69	0.0061
LFK12	1738.3081	1	1738.3081	7.69	0.0061
Residual	44767.903	198	226.10052		
Total	46506.211	199	233.69955		

margins LFK12 nach anova V_qrt LFK12 if LFK12 !=0

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 200

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

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|              Delta-method
|      Margin   Std. Err.    t    P>|t|    [95% Conf. Interval]
-----+-----
 LFK12 |
  1 <=50 |   45.05808   1.974407   22.82  0.000   41.16452   48.95165
  2 >50  |   51.55519   1.261847   40.86  0.000   49.06681   54.04358
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```

Variables that uniquely identify margins: LFK12

margins LFK12, pwcompare(effects) mcompare(bonferroni) nach anova V_qrt LFK12 if LFK12 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 200

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

note: option bonferroni ignored since there is only one comparison

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|              Delta-method   Unadjusted   Unadjusted
|      Contrast   Std. Err.    t    P>|t|    [95% Conf. Interval]
-----+-----
 LFK12 |
  2 >50 vs 1 <=50 |   6.49711   2.343191   2.77  0.006   1.876297   11.11792
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```

Variables that uniquely identify margins:

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.

(file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_LFK12.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

FAKTOR: LF <=50, 50-200, >200 (LFK13)

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+-----+
| Key |
+-----+
| frequency |
| expected frequency |
+-----+

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LF <=50, | V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]
50-200, >200 | unteres Q   mittlere   oberes Qu |      Total
-----+-----
<=50ha (1) |      19      33      6 |      58
|      14.8    29.3    13.9 |      58.0
-----+-----
50-200ha (2) |      26      48      23 |      97
|      24.7    49.0    23.3 |      97.0
-----+-----

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-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
>200ha (3) |          6          20          19 |          45
           |         11.5         22.7         10.8 |         45.0
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
Total     |          51          101          48 |          200
           |         51.0         101.0         48.0 |         200.0
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
    
```

Pearson chi2(4) = 15.4273 Pr = 0.004
 margins LFK13 nach anova V_qrt LFK13 if LFK13 !=0

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 200
 Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

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-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
           |          Delta-method
           |          Margin  Std. Err.    t    P>|t|    [95% Conf. Interval]
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
 LFK13 |
<=50ha (1) |  45.05808   1.943061   23.19  0.000   41.22621   48.88995
50-200ha (2) |  49.2481    1.5025    32.78  0.000   46.28505   52.21115
>200ha (3) |  56.52826   2.205942   25.63  0.000   52.17797   60.87856
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
    
```

Variables that uniquely identify margins: LFK13
 margins LFK13, pwcompare nach anova V_qrt LFK13 if LFK13 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 200
 Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

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-----+-----+-----
           |          Number of
           |          Comparisons
-----+-----+-----
 LFK13 |          3
-----+-----+-----
    
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-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
           |          Delta-method   Bonferroni   Bonferroni
           |          Contrast  Std. Err.    t    P>|t|    [95% Conf. Interval]
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
 LFK13 |
50-200ha (2) vs <=50ha (1) |  4.190015   2.456215   1.71  0.269   -1.740753   10.12078
>200ha (3) vs <=50ha (1) |  11.47018   2.939671   3.90  0.000   4.372061   18.5683
>200ha (3) vs 50-200ha (2) |  7.280166   2.669024   2.73  0.021   .8355507   13.72478
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----
    
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Variables that uniquely identify margins: _pw

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
 (file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_LFK13.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)
 (file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_box_V_qrt_LFK13_.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

FAKTOR: LF <=50, 50-200, >200 (LFK13) UND BEWIRTSCHAFTUNGSFORM (Un06)

Number of obs = 196 R-squared = 0.1150
 Root MSE = 14.4795 Adj R-squared = 0.1012

Source	Partial SS	df	MS	F	Prob>F
Model	5232.2974	3	1744.0991	8.32	0.0000
LFK13	3851.3117	2	1925.6559	9.18	0.0002
Un06	1954.1151	1	1954.1151	9.32	0.0026
Residual	40253.856	192	209.6555		
Total	45486.153	195	233.26232		

margins LFK13 Un06 nach anova V_qrt LFK13 if LFK13 !=0
 (2 observations deleted)

Predictive margins Number of obs = 196

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Margin	Delta-method Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
LFK13						
<=50ha (1)	44.32045	1.91654	23.13	0.000	40.54027	48.10062
50-200ha (2)	49.34666	1.496266	32.98	0.000	46.39543	52.29789
>200ha (3)	56.80868	2.186287	25.98	0.000	52.49645	61.1209
Un06						
Konventionell	48.61506	1.077201	45.13	0.000	46.49039	50.73972
Ökolandbau	60.62859	3.778201	16.05	0.000	53.17648	68.0807

margins LFK13 Un06, pwcompare(effects) mcompare(bonferroni) nach anova V_qrt LFK13 Un06 if LFK13 !=0 usw

Pairwise comparisons of predictive margins Number of obs = 196

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

| Number of

Comparisons	
LFK13	3
Un06	1

	Delta-method		Bonferroni		Bonferroni	
	Contrast	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
LFK13						
50-200ha (2) vs <=50ha (1)	5.026213	2.440557	2.06	0.122	-.8680689	10.9205
>200ha (3) vs <=50ha (1)	12.48823	2.917545	4.28	0.000	5.441956	19.5345
>200ha (3) vs 50-200ha (2)	7.462017	2.645034	2.82	0.016	1.073895	13.85014
Un06						
Ökolandbau vs Konventionell	12.01353	3.935037	3.05	0.003	4.252081	19.77499

FAKTOR: LF <=50, 50-200, 200-300,>300 (LFK14)

LF <=50, 50-200, 200-300,>300	V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]			Total
00	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
1 <=50	19	33	6	58
2 50-200	25	48	23	96
3 200-300	2	8	2	12
4 >300	4	12	17	33
Total	50	101	48	199

Key	
frequency	
expected frequency	

LF <=50, 50-200, 200-300,>300	V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]			Total
00	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
1 <=50	19	33	6	58
	14.6	29.4	14.0	58.0

2 50-200	25	48	23	96
	24.1	48.7	23.2	96.0
3 200-300	2	8	2	12
	3.0	6.1	2.9	12.0
4 >300	4	12	17	33
	8.3	16.7	8.0	33.0
Total	50	101	48	199
	50.0	101.0	48.0	199.0

Pearson chi2(6) = 21.4349 Pr = 0.002

Number of obs = 199 R-squared = 0.0838
 Root MSE = 14.7351 Adj R-squared = 0.0697

Source	Partial SS	df	MS	F	Prob>F
Model	3870.7317	3	1290.2439	5.94	0.0007
LFK14	3870.7317	3	1290.2439	5.94	0.0007
Residual	42339.252	195	217.12437		
Total	46209.984	198	233.38376		

margins LFK14 nach anova V_qrt LFK14 if LFK14 !=0

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 199

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Margin	Delta-method Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
LFK14					
1 <=50	45.05808	1.934819	23.29	0.000	41.24223 48.87394
2 50-200	49.42253	1.503899	32.86	0.000	46.45653 52.38852
3 200-300	50.9122	4.253669	11.97	0.000	42.5231 59.3013
4 >300	58.57047	2.565059	22.83	0.000	53.51165 63.62929

Variables that uniquely identify margins: LFK14

margins LFK14 if LFK14 >=0, pwcompare(effects) mcompare(noadjust) nach anova V_qrt LFK14 if LFK14 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 199

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

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	Contrast	Delta-method Std. Err.	Unadjusted t	Unadjusted P> t	Unadjusted [95% Conf. Interval]	
-----+-----						
LFK14						
2 50-200 vs 1 <=50	4.364445	2.450558	1.78	0.076	-.4685564	9.197445
3 200-300 vs 1 <=50	5.854119	4.673031	1.25	0.212	-3.362052	15.07029
4 >300 vs 1 <=50	13.51239	3.21295	4.21	0.000	7.175792	19.84898
3 200-300 vs 2 50-200	1.489674	4.511697	0.33	0.742	-7.408313	10.38766
4 >300 vs 2 50-200	9.147941	2.973422	3.08	0.002	3.283746	15.01214
4 >300 vs 3 200-300	7.658267	4.967215	1.54	0.125	-2.138095	17.45463

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margins LFK14 if LFK14 >=0, pwcompare(effects) mcompare(bonferroni) nach anova V_qrt LFK14 if LFK14 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 199

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

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	Number of Comparisons
-----+-----	
LFK14	6

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-----+-----
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	Contrast	Delta-method Std. Err.	Bonferroni t	Bonferroni P> t	Bonferroni [95% Conf. Interval]	
-----+-----						
LFK14						
2 50-200 vs 1 <=50	4.364445	2.450558	1.78	0.459	-2.167376	10.89627
3 200-300 vs 1 <=50	5.854119	4.673031	1.25	1.000	-6.601575	18.30981
4 >300 vs 1 <=50	13.51239	3.21295	4.21	0.000	4.948453	22.07632
3 200-300 vs 2 50-200	1.489674	4.511697	0.33	1.000	-10.53599	13.51534
4 >300 vs 2 50-200	9.147941	2.973422	3.08	0.014	1.222457	17.07343
4 >300 vs 3 200-300	7.658267	4.967215	1.54	0.749	-5.581556	20.89809

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Variables that uniquely identify margins: _pw

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
 (file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_LFK14.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

FAKTOR: H. B-Abschlussklasse (Un11_01c)

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Key

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frequency
expected frequency

H. B-Abschlussklasse	V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]			Total
	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
-9 n.a.	8	10	0	18
	4.5	9.1	4.4	18.0
1 sonstige	6	14	3	23
	5.8	11.6	5.6	23.0
2 nichtakadem Fachaus	16	31	21	68
	17.0	34.3	16.7	68.0
3 akadem. Ausbild.	21	48	26	95
	23.8	48.0	23.3	95.0
Total	51	103	50	204
	51.0	103.0	50.0	204.0

Pearson chi2(6) = 11.1052 Pr = 0.085

Number of obs = 186 R-squared = 0.0133
 Root MSE = 15.59 Adj R-squared = 0.0025

Source	Partial SS	df	MS	F	Prob>F
Model	600.43202	2	300.21601	1.24	0.2932
Un11_01c	600.43202	2	300.21601	1.24	0.2932
Residual	44477.943	183	243.04887		
Total	45078.375	185	243.66689		

margins Un11_01c nach anova V_qrt Un11_01c if Un11_01c !=0
 (18 observations deleted)

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 186

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Delta-method				
	Margin	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Un11_01c					

1 sonstige	46.32104	3.250745	14.25	0.000	39.90728	52.73479
2 nichtakadem Fachausbildung	52.23101	1.890568	27.63	0.000	48.50089	55.96112
3 akadem. Ausbild.	50.79118	1.599503	31.75	0.000	47.63534	53.94702

Variables that uniquely identify margins: Un11_01c
 margins Un11_01c, pwcompare(effects) mcompare(bonferroni) nach anova V_qrt Un11_01c if Un11_01c !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 186

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Number of Comparisons
Un11_01c	3

	Contrast	Delta-method Std. Err.	Bonferroni t	Bonferroni P> t	Bonferroni [95% Conf. Interval]
Un11_01c					
2 nichtakadem Fachausbildung vs 1 sonstige	5.909972	3.760531	1.57	0.353	-3.176177 14.99612
3 akadem. Ausbild. vs 1 sonstige	4.470143	3.622948	1.23	0.657	-4.283579 13.22387
3 akadem. Ausbild. vs 2 nichtakadem Fachausbildung	-1.439828	2.47642	-0.58	1.000	-7.423325 4.543668

Variables that uniquely identify margins: _pw

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
 (file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_Un11_01c.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

FAKTOR: Lage (Un08)

Key
frequency
expected frequency

Lage	V_qrt-Vielfaltssklasse [P25, P75]			Total
	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
Schlecht	3	2	1	6
	1.5	3.0	1.5	6.0

Weniger gut	3	17	4	24
	6.0	12.1	5.9	24.0
Befriedigend	27	44	19	90
	22.5	45.4	22.1	90.0
Gut	16	36	22	74
	18.5	37.4	18.1	74.0
Sehr gut	2	4	4	10
	2.5	5.0	2.5	10.0
Total	51	103	50	204
	51.0	103.0	50.0	204.0

Pearson chi2(8) = 9.9469 Pr = 0.269

Number of obs = 204 R-squared = 0.0119
 Root MSE = 15.422 Adj R-squared = -0.0080

Source	Partial SS	df	MS	F	Prob>F
Model	569.11468	4	142.27867	0.60	0.6643
Un08	569.11468	4	142.27867	0.60	0.6643
Residual	47329.508	199	237.83672		
Total	47898.623	203	235.95381		

margins Un08 nach anova V_qrt Un08 if Un08 !=0
 (0 observations deleted)

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 204

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Margin	Delta-method Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Un08					
Schlecht	44.94741	6.295987	7.14	0.000	32.53199 57.36282
Weniger gut	50.43491	3.147994	16.02	0.000	44.22721 56.64262
Befriedigend	48.58335	1.625617	29.89	0.000	45.3777 51.78899
Gut	51.42058	1.792766	28.68	0.000	47.88532 54.95583
Sehr gut	52.86963	4.876851	10.84	0.000	43.25269 62.48657

Variables that uniquely identify margins: Un08
 margins Un08, pwcompare nach anova V_qrt Un08 if Un08 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 204

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Number of Comparisons
Un08	10

	Delta-method Contrast	Std. Err.	Bonferroni t	P> t	Bonferroni [95% Conf. Interval]	
Un08						
Weniger gut vs Schlecht	5.487507	7.039128	0.78	1.000	-14.49428 25.46929	
Befriedigend vs Schlecht	3.635941	6.502468	0.56	1.000	-14.82244 22.09432	
Gut vs Schlecht	6.473169	6.546256	0.99	1.000	-12.10951 25.05585	
Sehr gut vs Schlecht	7.922223	7.963864	0.99	1.000	-14.68459 30.52903	
Befriedigend vs Weniger gut	-1.851566	3.54295	-0.52	1.000	-11.90884 8.205712	
Gut vs Weniger gut	.9856627	3.622689	0.27	1.000	-9.297968 11.26929	
Sehr gut vs Weniger gut	2.434716	5.804613	0.42	1.000	-14.04269 18.91212	
Gut vs Befriedigend	2.837229	2.42005	1.17	1.000	-4.032502 9.70696	
Sehr gut vs Befriedigend	4.286282	5.140652	0.83	1.000	-10.30635 18.87891	
Sehr gut vs Gut	1.449053	5.195929	0.28	1.000	-13.30049 16.1986	

Variables that uniquely identify margins: _pw

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
 (file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_Un08.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

FAKTOR: Zukunft (Un09)

Gehen Sie davon aus, dass Ihr Betrieb auch noch in 15 Jahren existiert?

Key	frequency	expected frequency

V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]	Total
Zukunft unteres Q mittlere oberes Qu	

Nein (1)	3	7	2	12
	3.0	6.1	2.9	12.0
Eher nein (2)	11	17	5	33
	8.3	16.7	8.1	33.0
Eher ja (3)	24	46	14	84
	21.0	42.4	20.6	84.0
ja (4)	13	33	29	75
	18.8	37.9	18.4	75.0
Total	51	103	50	204
	51.0	103.0	50.0	204.0

Pearson chi2(6) = 13.9122 Pr = 0.031

Number of obs = 204 R-squared = 0.0837
 Root MSE = 14.814 Adj R-squared = 0.0699

Source	Partial SS	df	MS	F	Prob>F
Model	4007.4097	3	1335.8032	6.09	0.0006
Un09	4007.4097	3	1335.8032	6.09	0.0006
Residual	43891.213	200	219.45606		
Total	47898.623	203	235.95381		

margins Un09 nach anova V_qrt Un09 if Un09 !=0
 (0 observations deleted)

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 204

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Margin	Delta-method Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Un09					
Nein (1)	45.27186	4.276448	10.59	0.000	36.83915 53.70457
Eher nein (2)	46.05908	2.578795	17.86	0.000	40.97396 51.14419
Eher ja (3)	46.95862	1.616345	29.05	0.000	43.77135 50.14588
ja (4)	55.71609	1.710579	32.57	0.000	52.34301 59.08918

Variables that uniquely identify margins: Un09

margins Un09, pwcompare nach anova V_qrt Un09 if Un09 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 204

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

```
-----
          |      Number of
          |      Comparisons
-----+-----
Un09 |              6
-----
```

```
-----
          |      Delta-method      Bonferroni      Bonferroni
          |      Contrast      Std. Err.      t      P>|t|      [95% Conf. Interval]
-----+-----
Un09 |
Eher nein (2) vs Nein (1) |      .7872143      4.993815      0.16      1.000      -12.52008      14.09451
Eher ja (3) vs Nein (1) |      1.686756      4.571715      0.37      1.000      -10.49575      13.86926
ja (4) vs Nein (1) |      10.44423      4.605875      2.27      0.147      -1.829304      22.71776
Eher ja (3) vs Eher nein (2) |      .899542      3.043478      0.30      1.000      -7.210583      9.009667
ja (4) vs Eher nein (2) |      9.657016      3.094554      3.12      0.012      1.410784      17.90325
ja (4) vs Eher ja (3) |      8.757474      2.353434      3.72      0.002      2.486145      15.0288
-----
```

Variables that uniquely identify margins: _pw

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
(file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_Un09.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)
Tierhaltung Viehbesatzklassen

FAKTOR: Vieh 0,<=10,>10 (ViehBesK12)

```
-----
Vieh |
0,<=10,>10 |      Freq.      Percent      Cum.
-----+-----
0 |      57      27.94      27.94
<=10 |      17      8.33      36.27
>10 |      130      63.73      100.00
-----+-----
Total |      204      100.00
-----
```

```
+-----+
| Key |
+-----+
| frequency |
| expected frequency |
+-----+
```

+-----+

Vieh	V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]			Total
0, <=10, >10	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
0	17 14.3	27 28.8	13 14.0	57 57.0
<=10	3 4.3	13 8.6	1 4.2	17 17.0
>10	31 32.5	63 65.6	36 31.9	130 130.0
Total	51 51.0	103 103.0	50 50.0	204 204.0

Pearson chi2(4) = 6.4675 Pr = 0.167

Number of obs = 204 R-squared = 0.0100
 Root MSE = 15.3598 Adj R-squared = 0.0001

Source	Partial SS	df	MS	F	Prob>F
Model	477.94811	2	238.97405	1.01	0.3650
ViehBesK12	477.94811	2	238.97405	1.01	0.3650
Residual	47420.675	201	235.92375		
Total	47898.623	203	235.95381		

margins ViehBesK12 nach anova V_qrt ViehBesK12 if ViehBesK12 !=0
 (0 observations deleted)

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 204

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Delta-method					
	Margin	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
ViehBesK12						
0	48.3471	2.034456	23.76	0.000	44.33548	52.35871
<=10	46.73992	3.725301	12.55	0.000	39.39424	54.08561
>10	51.04676	1.347144	37.89	0.000	48.39041	53.70311

Variables that uniquely identify margins: ViehBesK12

margins ViehBesK12, pwcompare nach anova V_qrt ViehBesK12 if ViehBesK12 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 204

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

```

-----
      |      Number of
      |      Comparisons
-----+-----
ViehBesK12 |      3
-----
  
```

```

-----
      |      Delta-method      Bonferroni      Bonferroni
      |      Contrast  Std. Err.      t      P>|t|      [95% Conf. Interval]
-----+-----
ViehBesK12 |
<=10 vs 0 | -1.607175   4.24463   -0.38   1.000   -11.85449   8.640139
 >10 vs 0 |  2.699665   2.440043    1.11   0.810   -3.191047   8.590376
>10 vs <=10 |  4.306839   3.961397    1.09   0.835   -5.256699  13.87038
-----
  
```

Variables that uniquely identify margins: _pw

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
 (file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_ViehBesK12.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

FAKTOR: Vieh 0,<=10,10-300,>300 (ViehBesK13)

```

-----
      Vieh |
0,<=10,10- | V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]
300,>300 | unteres Q  mittlere  oberes Qu |      Total
-----+-----
      0 |      17      27      13 |      57
      <=10 |      3      13      1 |      17
      10-300 |      21      50      21 |      92
      >300 |      10      13      15 |      38
-----+-----
      Total |      51      103      50 |      204
-----
  
```

```

-----+-----
| Key |
|-----|
|      frequency |
| expected frequency |
-----+-----
  
```

Vieh	V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]			Total
0, <=10, 10-300, >300	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
0	17	27	13	57
	14.3	28.8	14.0	57.0
<=10	3	13	1	17
	4.3	8.6	4.2	17.0
10-300	21	50	21	92
	23.0	46.5	22.5	92.0
>300	10	13	15	38
	9.5	19.2	9.3	38.0
Total	51	103	50	204
	51.0	103.0	50.0	204.0

Pearson chi2(6) = 11.7992 Pr = 0.067

Number of obs = 204 R-squared = 0.0168
 Root MSE = 15.345 Adj R-squared = 0.0021

Source	Partial SS	df	MS	F	Prob>F
Model	804.8829	3	268.2943	1.14	0.3343
ViehBesK13	804.8829	3	268.2943	1.14	0.3343
Residual	47093.74	200	235.4687		
Total	47898.623	203	235.95381		

margins ViehBesK13 nach anova V_qrt ViehBesK13 if ViehBesK13 !=0
 (0 observations deleted)

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 204

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Delta-method				
	Margin	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
ViehBesK13					
0	48.3471	2.032493	23.79	0.000	44.33923 52.35496
<=10	46.73992	3.721707	12.56	0.000	39.4011 54.07874
10-300	50.02757	1.599826	31.27	0.000	46.87288 53.18226
>300	53.51428	2.489286	21.50	0.000	48.60567 58.4229

Variables that uniquely identify margins: ViehBesK13

margins ViehBesK13, pwcompare nach anova V_qrt ViehBesK13 if ViehBesK13 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 204

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Number of Comparisons
ViehBesK13	6

	Contrast	Delta-method Std. Err.	Bonferroni t	Bonferroni P> t	Bonferroni [95% Conf. Interval]
ViehBesK13					
<=10 vs 0	-1.607175	4.240534	-0.38	1.000	-12.90716 9.692814
10-300 vs 0	1.680471	2.586595	0.65	1.000	-5.212173 8.573115
>300 vs 0	5.167187	3.213654	1.61	0.657	-3.396418 13.73079
10-300 vs <=10	3.287646	4.050993	0.81	1.000	-7.507262 14.08255
>300 vs <=10	6.774361	4.47746	1.51	0.791	-5.156976 18.7057
>300 vs 10-300	3.486716	2.959052	1.18	1.000	-4.398435 11.37187

Variables that uniquely identify margins: _pw

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
 (file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_ViehBesK13.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

FAKTOR: Region(NW/SW/O) (region)

Region(NW/SW/O)	V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]			Total
	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
Sued (BW, BY, HE, RP)	15	42	14	71
Ost (BB, MV, TH, SN, NW (NI, NRW, SH)	2	7	11	20
	30	52	23	105
Total	47	101	48	196

Pearson chi2(4) = 13.2864 Pr = 0.010

Number of obs = 196 R-squared = 0.0521

Root MSE = 15.1344 Adj R-squared = 0.0423

Source	Partial SS	df	MS	F	Prob>F
Model	2430.2298	2	1215.1149	5.30	0.0057
region	2430.2298	2	1215.1149	5.30	0.0057
Residual	44206.952	193	229.05156		
Total	46637.181	195	239.16503		

margins region nach anova V_qrt region if region !=0
(0 observations deleted)

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 196

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Delta-method		t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
	Margin	Std. Err.				
region						
Sued (BW, BY, HE, RP)	49.5462	1.796129	27.58	0.000	46.00364	53.08876
Ost (BB, MV, TH, SN, ST)	60.43437	3.384166	17.86	0.000	53.75967	67.10906
NW (NI, NRW, SH)	48.48906	1.476971	32.83	0.000	45.57598	51.40214

Variables that uniquely identify margins: region
margins region, pwcompare nach anova V_qrt region if region !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 196

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Number of Comparisons
region	3

	Contrast	Delta-method Std. Err.	Bonferroni t	Bonferroni P> t	Bonferroni [95% Conf. Interval]	
region						
Ost (BB, MV, TH, SN, ST) vs Sued (BW, BY, HE, RP)	10.88816	3.831273	2.84	0.015	1.635533	20.14079
NW (NI, NRW, SH) vs Sued (BW, BY, HE, RP)	-1.057142	2.325408	-0.45	1.000	-6.673066	4.558782

```
NW (NI, NRW, SH) vs Ost (BB, MV, TH, SN, ST) | -11.94531  3.692428  -3.24  0.004  -20.86262  -3.027992
```

Variables that uniquely identify margins: _pw

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
(file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_region.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

FAKTOR: Kommunikation CSR (Z107)

Kommunikati on CSR	V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]			Total
	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
1 gar nicht	21	26	7	54
2 w gr Ausm	24	57	26	107
3 gr Ausm	4	16	15	35
4 s gr Ausm	2	4	2	8
Total	51	103	50	204

Pearson chi2(6) = 15.1562 Pr = 0.019
margins Z107 nach anova V_qrt Z107 if Z107 !=0
(0 observations deleted)

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 204

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Delta-method				
	Margin	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Z107					
1 gar nicht	44.5046	2.04134	21.80	0.000	40.47929 48.52991
2 w gr Ausm	50.54299	1.450175	34.85	0.000	47.6834 53.40258
3 gr Ausm	55.77331	2.535585	22.00	0.000	50.7734 60.77322
4 s gr Ausm	52.87852	5.303556	9.97	0.000	42.42045 63.33658

Variables that uniquely identify margins: Z107
margins Z107, pwcompare nach anova V_qrt Z107 if Z107 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 204

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

| Number of

```

      | Comparisons
-----+-----
      Z107 |           6
-----

```

	Delta-method Contrast	Std. Err.	Bonferroni t	Bonferroni P> t	Bonferroni [95% Conf. Interval]
Z107					
2 w gr Ausm vs 1 gar nicht	6.038385	2.504012	2.41	0.101	-.6341949 12.71097
3 gr Ausm vs 1 gar nicht	11.2687	3.25519	3.46	0.004	2.594417 19.94299
4 s gr Ausm vs 1 gar nicht	8.373911	5.682849	1.47	0.853	-6.769496 23.51732
3 gr Ausm vs 2 w gr Ausm	5.230318	2.920992	1.79	0.449	-2.553414 13.01405
4 s gr Ausm vs 2 w gr Ausm	2.335526	5.498247	0.42	1.000	-12.31596 16.98701
4 s gr Ausm vs 3 gr Ausm	-2.894792	5.878512	-0.49	1.000	-18.55959 12.77001

Variables that uniquely identify margins: _pw

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
(file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_Z107.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

FAKTOR: Rechtsform (Un03)

Rechtsform	V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]			Total
	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
Nicht beantwortet	6	13	3	22
GbR	11	22	14	47
e.u.	12	19	11	42
GmbH	0	1	4	5
e.G.	4	2	4	10
a.g.	0	0	1	1
Anderes	18	46	13	77
Total	51	103	50	204

Pearson chi2(12) = 21.0951 Pr = 0.049
margins Un03 nach anova V_qrt Un03 if Un03 !=0
(22 observations deleted)

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 182

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

```

      | Delta-method

```

	Margin	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	

Un03						
GbR	52.24284	2.279755	22.92	0.000	47.74367	56.74202
e.u.	50.14682	2.411639	20.79	0.000	45.38736	54.90627
GmbH	68.28275	6.989595	9.77	0.000	54.48855	82.07696
e.G.	47.47263	4.94239	9.61	0.000	37.71865	57.2266
a.g.	61.44818	15.62921	3.93	0.000	30.6034	92.29297
Anderes	48.20931	1.781114	27.07	0.000	44.69422	51.7244

Variables that uniquely identify margins: Un03
 margins Un03, pwcompare nach anova V_qrt Un03 if Un03 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 182

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Number of Comparisons

Un03	15

	Contrast	Delta-method Std. Err.	Bonferroni t	Bonferroni P> t	Bonferroni [95% Conf. Interval]	

Un03						
e.u. vs GbR	-2.096027	3.318627	-0.63	1.000	-11.9716	7.779541
GmbH vs GbR	16.03991	7.351988	2.18	0.457	-5.838131	37.91795
e.G. vs GbR	-4.770217	5.44284	-0.88	1.000	-20.96701	11.42658
a.g. vs GbR	9.205342	15.7946	0.58	1.000	-37.79623	56.20691
Anderes vs GbR	-4.033531	2.893034	-1.39	1.000	-12.64262	4.575559
GmbH vs e.u.	18.13594	7.393947	2.45	0.227	-3.866965	40.13884
e.G. vs e.u.	-2.674189	5.499384	-0.49	1.000	-19.03925	13.69087
a.g. vs e.u.	11.30137	15.81418	0.71	1.000	-35.75845	58.36119
Anderes vs e.u.	-1.937503	2.998061	-0.65	1.000	-10.85913	6.984125
e.G. vs GmbH	-20.81013	8.560471	-2.43	0.241	-46.28437	4.664118
a.g. vs GmbH	-6.834567	17.12094	-0.40	1.000	-57.78305	44.11392
Anderes vs GmbH	-20.07344	7.212961	-2.78	0.090	-41.53776	1.390885
a.g. vs e.G.	13.97556	16.39205	0.85	1.000	-34.8039	62.75502
Anderes vs e.G.	.7366861	5.253531	0.14	1.000	-14.89677	16.37014
Anderes vs a.g.	-13.23887	15.73037	-0.84	1.000	-60.0493	33.57156

Variables that uniquely identify margins: _pw

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
 (file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_Un03.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

Rechtsform	Rechtsform umkodiert									Total
	-9 Nicht	1 GbR	2 Einzelu	3 GmbH	4 e.G.	5 AG	6 KG	7 Verschi	8 Anderes	
Nicht beantwortet	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22
GbR	0	47	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	47
e.u.	0	0	42	0	0	0	0	0	0	42
GmbH	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	5
e.G.	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	10
a.g.	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
Anderes	0	0	46	0	0	0	6	5	20	77
Total	22	47	88	5	10	1	6	5	20	204

(94 differences between Un03_neu and Un03_neu1)

Rechtsform umkodiert	Rechtsf. aggr.					Total
	-9 n. b.	1 Jur. Pe	2 Einzelu	3 Personne	4 Andere	
-9 Nicht beantwortet	22	0	0	0	0	22
1 GbR	0	0	0	47	0	47
2 Einzelunternehmen	0	0	88	0	0	88
3 GmbH	0	5	0	0	0	5
4 e.G.	0	10	0	0	0	10
5 AG	0	1	0	0	0	1
6 KG	0	0	0	6	0	6
7 Verschiedene Rechts	0	0	0	0	5	5
8 Anderes	0	0	0	0	20	20
Total	22	16	88	53	25	204

FAKTOR: Rechtsf. aggr. (Un03_neu1)

Rechtsf. aggr.	V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]			Total
	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
1 Jur. Pers.	4	3	9	16
2 Einzeluntern.	21	47	20	88
3 Personengesellsch.	14	23	16	53
4 Andere Rechtsf.	6	17	2	25
Total	45	90	47	182

Pearson $\chi^2(6) = 15.0832$ Pr = 0.020

margins Un03_neu1 nach anova V_qrt Un03_neu1 if Un03_neu1 !=0
 (22 observations deleted)

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 182

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Delta-method		t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
	Margin	Std. Err.				
Un03_neu1						
1 Jur. Pers.	54.84926	3.954794	13.87	0.000	47.04495	62.65358
2 Einzeluntern.	49.28074	1.68633	29.22	0.000	45.95297	52.60851
3 Personengesellsch.	51.94813	2.172931	23.91	0.000	47.66011	56.23615
4 Andere Rechtsf.	47.34963	3.163835	14.97	0.000	41.10618	53.59308

Variables that uniquely identify margins: Un03_neu1
 margins Un03_neu1, pwcompare nach anova V_qrt Un03_neu1 if Un03_neu1 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 182

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Number of Comparisons
Un03_neu1	6

	Delta-method	Bonferroni	Bonferroni		
	Contrast	Std. Err.	t	P> t	
					[95% Conf. Interval]
Un03_neu1					
2 Einzeluntern. vs 1 Jur. Pers.	-5.568521	4.299314	-1.30	1.000	-17.03937 5.902333
3 Personengesellsch. vs 1 Jur. Pers.	-2.901133	4.51243	-0.64	1.000	-14.94059 9.138327
4 Andere Rechtsf. vs 1 Jur. Pers.	-7.499635	5.064608	-1.48	0.843	-21.01234 6.013071
3 Personengesellsch. vs 2 Einzeluntern.	2.667388	2.750516	0.97	1.000	-4.671169 10.00594
4 Andere Rechtsf. vs 2 Einzeluntern.	-1.931114	3.585186	-0.54	1.000	-11.49663 7.634399
4 Andere Rechtsf. vs 3 Personengesellsch.	-4.598502	3.838161	-1.20	1.000	-14.83897 5.641965

Variables that uniquely identify margins: _pw

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
 (file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_Un03_neu1.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

FAKTOR: Erwerbsform (Un04)

Erwerbsform	V_qrt-Vielfaltssklasse [P25, P75]			Total
	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
Haupterwerb	38	75	44	157
Nebenerwerb	13	27	6	46
Total	51	102	50	203

Pearson chi2(2) = 4.3203 Pr = 0.115
(1 observation deleted)
margins Un04 nach anova V_qrt Un04 if Un04 !=0

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 203

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Delta-method				
	Margin	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Un04					
Haupterwerb	51.1389	1.217862	41.99	0.000	48.73748 53.54033
Nebenerwerb	45.6882	2.249929	20.31	0.000	41.25171 50.12469

Variables that uniquely identify margins: Un04
margins Un04, pwcompare mcompare(noadjust) nach anova V_qrt Un04 if Un04 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 203

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Contrast	Delta-method	Unadjusted		Unadjusted	
		Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
Un04						
Nebenerwerb vs Haupterwerb	-5.450701	2.558392	-2.13	0.034	-10.49543 -.4059708	

margins Un04, pwcompare mcompare(bonferroni) nach anova V_qrt Un04 if Un04 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 203

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

note: option bonferroni ignored since there is only one comparison

	Delta-method	Unadjusted	Unadjusted
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	Contrast	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
Un04						
Nebenerwerb vs Haupterwerb	-5.450701	2.558392	-2.13	0.034	-10.49543	-.4059708

Variables that uniquely identify margins:

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
 (file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_Un04.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

FAKTOR: Betriebsform (Un06 if Un06 != -9 & Un06!=3)

Betriebsform	V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]			Total
	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
Konventionell	51	93	41	185
Ökolandbau	0	9	6	15
Total	51	102	47	200

Pearson chi2(2) = 6.2714 Pr = 0.043
 anova V_qrt Un06 if Un06 != -9 & Un06!=3

Number of obs = 200 R-squared = 0.0292
 Root MSE = 15.1189 Adj R-squared = 0.0243

Source	Partial SS	df	MS	F	Prob>F
Model	1359.3075	1	1359.3075	5.95	0.0156
Un06	1359.3075	1	1359.3075	5.95	0.0156
Residual	45258.796	198	228.57978		
Total	46618.103	199	234.26182		

margins Un06 nach anova V_qrt Un06 if Un06 !=0
 (0 observations deleted)

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 200

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Delta-method		t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Margin	Std. Err.				
Un06					

Konventionell	48.8572	1.11156	43.95	0.000	46.66518	51.04921
Ökolandbau	58.75508	3.903672	15.05	0.000	51.05697	66.45319

Variables that uniquely identify margins: Un06
 margins Un06, pwcompare nach anova V_qrt Un06 if Un06 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 200

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

note: option bonferroni ignored since there is only one comparison

	Contrast	Delta-method Std. Err.	Unadjusted t	P> t	Unadjusted [95% Conf. Interval]	
Un06						
Ökolandbau vs Konventionell	9.897884	4.058844	2.44	0.016	1.893772	17.902

Variables that uniquely identify margins:

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
 (file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_Un06.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

Familienbetrieb	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Nein	11	5.39	5.39
Teilweise	17	8.33	13.73
Ja	176	86.27	100.00
Total	204	100.00	

FAKTOR: Familienbetrieb (Un10)

Familienbetrieb	V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]			Total
	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	
Nein	4	4	3	11
Teilweise	6	9	2	17
Ja	41	90	45	176
Total	51	103	50	204

Pearson chi2(4) = 3.2042 Pr = 0.524
 margins Un10 nach anova V_qrt Un10 if Un10 !=0
 (0 observations deleted)

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 204

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

		Delta-method		t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
	Margin	Std. Err.					
Un10							
Nein	45.89106	4.628495	9.91	0.000	36.76442	55.01769	
Teilweise	45.87799	3.72316	12.32	0.000	38.53653	53.21945	
Ja	50.57793	1.157124	43.71	0.000	48.29627	52.85959	

Variables that uniquely identify margins: Un10
 margins Un10, pwcompare nach anova V_qrt Un10 if Un10 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 204

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Number of Comparisons
Un10	3

	Delta-method	Bonferroni	Bonferroni		
	Contrast	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Un10					
Teilweise vs Nein	-.0130679	5.940108	-0.00	1.000	-14.35358 14.32744
Ja vs Nein	4.68687	4.770943	0.98	0.981	-6.831061 16.2048
Ja vs Teilweise	4.699938	3.898827	1.21	0.688	-4.712545 14.11242

Variables that uniquely identify margins: _pw

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
 (file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_Un10.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

FAKTOR: Alter (Un12 if Un12 != -9 & inlist(Bd6_Position,2,3,4))

Alter	V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]			Total
	unteres Q	mittlere	oberes Qu	

20-30 Jahre	6	6	3	15
30-40 Jahre	10	20	10	40
40-50 Jahre	12	26	13	51
50-65 Jahre	19	36	20	75
> 65 Jahre	0	0	1	1
-----+-----+-----				
Total	47	88	47	182

Pearson chi2(8) = 4.7051 Pr = 0.789

anova V_qrt Un12 if Un12 != -9 & inlist(Bd6_Position,2,3,4)

Number of obs = 182 R-squared = 0.0246
 Root MSE = 15.7097 Adj R-squared = 0.0026

Source	Partial SS	df	MS	F	Prob>F
-----+-----					
Model	1103.9418	4	275.98544	1.12	0.3494
Un12	1103.9418	4	275.98544	1.12	0.3494
Residual	43682.576	177	246.79421		
-----+-----					
Total	44786.518	181	247.43932		

margins Un12 nach anova V_qrt Un12 if Un12 !=0
 (0 observations deleted)

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 182

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Delta-method					
	Margin	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
-----+-----						
Un12						
20-30 Jahre	48.77915	4.056223	12.03	0.000	40.77436	56.78393
30-40 Jahre	48.84578	2.483919	19.66	0.000	43.94387	53.74769
40-50 Jahre	50.02721	2.199796	22.74	0.000	45.686	54.36841
50-65 Jahre	50.23301	1.813998	27.69	0.000	46.65317	53.81286
> 65 Jahre	82.01878	15.70969	5.22	0.000	51.01638	113.0212

Variables that uniquely identify margins: Un12

margins Un12, pwcompare nach anova V_qrt Un12 if Un12 !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 182

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

```

-----
|      Number of
|      Comparisons
-----+-----
Un12 |      10
-----

```

```

-----
|      Delta-method      Bonferroni      Bonferroni
|      Contrast      Std. Err.      t      P>|t|      [95% Conf. Interval]
-----+-----
Un12 |
30-40 Jahre vs 20-30 Jahre |      .0666374      4.756343      0.01      1.000      -13.45399      13.58727
40-50 Jahre vs 20-30 Jahre |      1.248062      4.614331      0.27      1.000      -11.86888      14.365
50-65 Jahre vs 20-30 Jahre |      1.453868      4.44337      0.33      1.000      -11.17709      14.08482
> 65 Jahre vs 20-30 Jahre |      33.23963      16.22489      2.05      0.420      -12.8821      79.36136
40-50 Jahre vs 30-40 Jahre |      1.181424      3.317975      0.36      1.000      -8.250425      10.61327
50-65 Jahre vs 30-40 Jahre |      1.387231      3.075784      0.45      1.000      -7.356153      10.13061
> 65 Jahre vs 30-40 Jahre |      33.17299      15.90484      2.09      0.384      -12.03895      78.38493
50-65 Jahre vs 40-50 Jahre |      .2058064      2.851261      0.07      1.000      -7.899338      8.310951
> 65 Jahre vs 40-50 Jahre |      31.99157      15.86295      2.02      0.452      -13.10129      77.08443
> 65 Jahre vs 50-65 Jahre |      31.78576      15.81407      2.01      0.460      -13.16814      76.73966
-----

```

Variables that uniquely identify margins: _pw

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
(file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_Un12.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

FAKTOR: Altersklassen (2) (Un12a if Un12a != -9 & inlist(Bd6_Position,2,3,4))

```

-----
Altersklas | V_qrt-Vielfaltsklasse [P25, P75]
sen (2) | unteres Q      mittlere      oberes Qu      Total
-----+-----
20-50 |      28      52      26 |      106
>50 |      19      36      21 |      76
-----+-----
Total |      47      88      47 |      182
-----

```

Pearson chi2(2) = 0.2255 Pr = 0.893
anova V_qrt Un12a if Un12a != -9 & inlist(Bd6_Position,2,3,4)

Number of obs = 182 R-squared = 0.0015
Root MSE = 15.7617 Adj R-squared = -0.0040

```

-----
Source | Partial SS      df      MS      F      Prob>F
-----+-----
Model | 68.772344      1      68.772344      0.28      0.5994
-----

```

Un12a	68.772344	1	68.772344	0.28	0.5994
Residual	44717.745	180	248.43192		

Total	44786.518	181	247.43932		

margins Un12a nach anova V_qrt Un12a if Un12a !=0
(0 observations deleted)

Adjusted predictions Number of obs = 182

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

	Delta-method		t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
	Margin	Std. Err.				
Un12a						
20-50	49.40477	1.530914	32.27	0.000	46.38393	52.42562
>50	50.65125	1.807994	28.02	0.000	47.08366	54.21884

Variables that uniquely identify margins: Un12a
margins Un12a, pwcompare nach anova V_qrt Un12a if Un12a !=0

Pairwise comparisons of adjusted predictions Number of obs = 182

Expression : Linear prediction, predict()

note: option bonferroni ignored since there is only one comparison

	Delta-method	Unadjusted	Unadjusted	Unadjusted	
	Contrast	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Un12a					
>50 vs 20-50	1.246473	2.36908	0.53	0.599	-3.428268 5.921214

Variables that uniquely identify margins:

_pw enumerates all pairwise comparisons; _pw0 enumerates the reference categories; _pw1 enumerates the comparison categories.
(file C:\Eigene Dateien\IAMO Cloud\CSRStep\stata\pic\csr3_191001_contrasts_V_qrt_Un12a.wmf written in Windows Metafile format)

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